

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.5.7

Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation road map

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Project Profile

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Publishable Summary

The current report for deliverable D5.7 is an update of deliverable D5.6 and it is produced in the context of BIO-SUSHY-WP5, **Task 5.4 – Standardisation activities**, in particular *subtask 5.4.2 – Contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments*

D5.8 “Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation road map” will collect the actions performed for the contribution to standardisation from BIO-SUSHY and the results obtained. The contribution to standardisation seeks to transfer selected results of BIO-SUSHY to standards (EN/CLC/ISO). D5.8 shall be delivered at M48, however it was considered that two previous versions were needed to first, define a strategy to proceed with this contribution (D5.6) and second, to record the actions and results of the interaction with the standardisation system (D5.7, present document) that will ease the subsequent contribution to standardisation.

The transfer of the results produced by the BIO-SUSHY project to standards that are widely recognized by the industry and developed in a system external to the Consortium will ease the market uptake of these results and impact beyond the duration of the project. Additionally, the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel towards the stakeholders represented in the standardisation committees.

D5.7 is based on the conclusions of D5.5 “Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards” and the strategy defined in D5.6. These deliverables included the information on the relevant existing and ongoing standards and the relevant standardisation technical committees to facilitate the use of existing knowledge and the compatibility and the interoperability of the results.

The Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE), as a National Standardisation Body (NSB), member of CEN-CENELEC and ISO-IEC, is a partner of BIO-SUSHY who will provide support regarding the standardisation tasks included in the project (WP5 “Measures to maximise impact”).

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
EN	European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardisation; International Standard
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardisation
NSB	National Standardisation Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee

1. Scope

This second version of the deliverable **“Report on the contribution to standardisation and standardisation roadmap”** records the actions performed and the results of the interaction with the standardisation system. These interactions are addressed to the standardisation committees previously identified (D5.6) where the relevant stakeholders in the pertinent fields are represented.

The **objectives** are to:

- Facilitate the subsequent contribution to standardisation allowing the related standardisation committees an advanced knowledge of BIO-SUSHY and to comment about the standardisation possibilities.
- Disseminate the results and objectives of BIO-SUSHY using the network of the standardisation community and to facilitate the subsequent contribution to standardisation.
- Gather any feedback that may come from the standardisation community regarding the development of BIO-SUSHY.

2. Strategy (extracted from D5.6)

The contribution to standardisation of BIO-SUSHY is based on the interaction with the relevant Standardisation Technical Committees and in the initiation of a standardisation process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in Figure 1 and the different steps are explained below.

Figure 1 – Strategy for the contribution to standardisation of BIO-SUSHY.

1.1. First contact with the standardisation technical committees

The objective of this first contact is to raise awareness about BIO-SUSHY among the relevant standardisation committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at European/International level are present in these committees, so the standardisation system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback will be asked for to gather any view, opinion or advice about the project and the standardisation possibilities and requirements. Additionally, these first contacts will be useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardisation process. Moreover, this first step will ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardisation committee.

1.2. Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the relevant CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC technical committees. Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: the impact/relevance of the standardisation works of the standardisation committees and the feasibility of initiating a standardisation process within a standardisation committee (versus initiating the standardisation process within a standardisation workshop, details are given below). The ways of interaction of the project with the standardisation committees include:

1. ***Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardisation committees.*** This allows to detect the initiation of standardisation works that can be relevant for BIO-SUSHY and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardisation activity.
2. ***Further contact with the standardisation committees to update the progress of BIO-SUSHY.*** This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardisation process, on the other hand this further contact is mandatory towards the standardisation committees directly covering (if it were the case) the subject that will be promoted by BIO-SUSHY to undergo a standardisation process.
3. ***The participation of one or more BIO-SUSHY partner in the standardisation technical committees.*** Standardisation is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardisation Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardization committee and is valuable if the standardisation process is going to be initiated within the standardisation committee.
4. ***The establishment of a formal liaison of BIO-SUSHY with the standardisation committees.*** It is recommended only when the work of the standardisation committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected. The figure of project liaison is recognized in CEN/CENELEC but it is not very effective in ISO/IEC, this shall be taken into account.

1.3. Standardisation process

The main objective of the standardisation activities in BIO-SUSHY is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners the feasible results to go through a standardisation process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardisation shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and IPR) and the standardisation context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardisation committees):

1. ***Development of a new standard within a standardisation workshop.*** A standardisation workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardisation committee but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures faster and more flexible. A standardisation workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardisation committees or when these committees are not interested in developing such standard (e.g. it does not fit in their work program). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardisation committee it shall be informed and allow for the launching of the standardization workshop.

Considering that the standardisation workshop option is interesting for BIO-SUSHY mainly in the European environment, the standardisation workshop will be named herein after as CEN Workshop or CENELEC Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN/CENELEC Workshop is called CEN Workshop Agreement or CENELEC Workshop Agreement, typically named as CWA. The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for the framework of the R&I projects.

2. ***Standardisation within a standardisation committee.*** It may be interesting or needed that the results of BIO-SUSHY go through the standardisation process and are standardized within a standardisation committee. The possible scenarios are:
 - a. ***Development of a new standard within a standardisation committee.*** When there is a result of BIO-SUSHY to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardisation committee and such committee decides to include this development in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardisation committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardisation committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.
 - b. ***Contribute to an on-going standard.*** As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardisation landscape it may be found that the results of BIO-SUSHY are covered

by an on-going standard but that these results do not fit into the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found in both, standards that are being developed from a new initiative and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.

- c. *Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review.* The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardisation committee.
- d. *Outline of a future standard.* Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardisation (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

2. Actions and results

The actions and the results for the implementation of the strategy described in the previous clause are detailed next.

2.1. First contact with the standardisation technical committees

The next actions have been performed for the implementation of the actions described in 2.1:

1. Selection of standardisation committees to contact

It shall be noticed that among the topics identified in D5.5, BIO-SUSHY innovation fields are:

- Novel bio-based coatings (sol-gel and powder)
- Water and oil repellent coating
- Validation of these coatings in three target markets: Textile, food packaging and packaging for cosmetic applications.

The contribution to these developments is based on 3 pillars: R&I (Research and Innovation) coating development, supported by computational modelling of coating performances, toxicity assessment and by SSbD (Safe and Sustainable-by-Design) methodology to ensure safety and environmental performances. For these three pillars, a relevant contribution to new standards is not expected in the project, but their consideration is useful in terms of compatibility of the developments of BIO-SUSHY. For this reason, among the different technical committees identified in the D5.5 with the contribution of all the consortium, six European (CEN) and four International (ISO) committees were contacted. Table 1 includes the topics and standardisation committees identified in D5.5 and the decision on those to be contacted with the objectives described in 2.1:

Table 1 – Standardisation committees relevant for further standardisation activities.

Subject	Technical committee	Contacted
Coatings	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	Yes
	ISO/TC 35/SC 15 – Protective coatings: concrete surface preparation and coating application	
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
Raw materials	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics	Yes
	CEN/ TC 411 – Bio-based products	
	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	No

Coating characterization	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
	ISO/TC 6 – Paper, board and pulps	
	CEN/TC 172 – Pulp, paper and board	
Case studies	ISO/TC 38 – Textiles	Yes
	CEN/TC 248 – Textiles and textile products	
	CEN/TC 194 – Utensil in contact with food	
	ISO/TC 217 – Cosmetics	
	CEN/TC 329 – Cosmetics	
Nanosafety issues	ISO/TC 229 – Nanotechnologies	No
	CEN/TC 352 – Nanotechnologies	
Toxicity evaluation	ISO/TC 146 – Air quality	No
	CEN/TC 264 – Air quality	
	ISO/TC 61 – Plastics	Yes
	CEN/TC 249 – Plastics	
	ISO/TC 219 – Floor coverings	
	CEN/TC 134 – Resilient and textile floor coverings	
	ISO/TC 35 – Paints and varnishes	
	CEN/TC 139 – Paints and varnishes	
	ISO/TC 147 – Water quality	No
Computational tools	ISO/IEC JTC 1 – Information technology	No
	ISO/TC 46 – Information and documentation	
	ISO/TC 171 – Document management application	
	ISO/TC 184 – Automation systems and integration	
	CEN/CLC JTC 21 – Artificial intelligence	
Life cycle	ISO/TC 207 – Environmental management	No

2. Definition of the information to provide and identification of contact details

The secretaries of the selected committees were addressed using the email model described in D5.6. The text for the communication includes:

- Brief introduction of the project.
- Explanation of the aim of the standardisation activities in the project. Presentation of UNE as part of the standardisation community and as the project partner leading these activities.
- Showing the link of the work developed in BIO-SUSHY with the relevant standardisation committee highlighting specific project objectives and relevant standards.
- Link to the BIO-SUSHY webpage.

In addition, a summary document prepared with the help of the coordinators was included in the communication summarizing the most important data of the project and the results achieved so far.

3. Replies from the selected standardisation committees

The selected standardisation committees (see table 1) were contacted by email. A reminder was needed in some cases.

The feedback received from each committee is detailed in the following table (Table 2).

Table 2 – Feedback from selected standardisation committees

Standardisation committee	Result
ISO/TC 35 "Paints and varnishes"	NOT INTERESTED <i>"the subject mentioned (Bio-Sushy) is not aligning with any of the running activities in the active groups if ISO/TC 35"</i>
CEN/TC 139 "Paints and varnishes"	<i>No response</i>
ISO/TC 61 "Plastics"	<i>No response</i>
CEN/TC 249 "Plastics"	<i>No response</i>
CEN/ TC 411 "Bio-based products"	<i>No response</i>
ISO/TC 38 "Textiles"	<i>No response</i>

<p>CEN/TC 248 "Textiles and textile products"</p>	<p><i>No response</i></p>
<p>CEN/TC 194 "Utensil in contact with food"</p>	<p>INTERESTED <i>"experts are interesting to get information, especially CEN/TC 194/WG 7 "Methods of test for monomers" could contribute."</i></p>
<p>CEN/TC 392 "Cosmetics"</p>	<p>INTERESTED <i>"I would like to confirm CEN/TC 392's interest in receiving the project results and further communication on the Bio-Sushy project at our next plenary meeting. These are usually held towards the end of the year (November/December 2024)."</i></p>
<p>ISO/TC 219 "Floor coverings"</p>	<p>No contacted because of the interest of the CEN/TC 134</p>
<p>CEN/TC 134 "Resilient and textile floor coverings"</p>	<p>INTERESTED <i>"I am happy to inform you that Mr Dirk Simoens, the convenor of CEN TC134 WG8 Textile floor coverings is interested in a closer cooperation with the BIO-SUSHY project."</i></p>

4. Analysis of results of the first contacts with the selected standardisation committees

Three of the Technical Committees (TCs) that were consulted expressed interest in the project. All of them are European TCs from CEN (CEN/TC 134, CEN/TC 194 and CEN/TC 392) and expressed a desire to be kept informed about the project's progress and to have the results and findings shared with them.

Considering the three use cases of the project, having positive feedback from European committees focused on each use case is valuable for the project. On one hand, it is a good dissemination channel since stakeholders in this specific field from different countries participate in these standardisation committees, on the other hand the view from these committees about the planned contributions to standardisation from the project will provide well-founded feedback.

The lack of response from the other TCs is not considered to have a significant impact, as their scope is much broader than the specific outcome to be developed in the project. Nevertheless, the European and International TCs related with textiles, as well as the European TC for paints and varnishes, will be consulted again with an update of the results obtained so far, to the best of their knowledge.

2.2. Subsequent interaction with the standardisation technical committees

The different actions included in this point are described following the structure of 2.2:

1. Follow-up of the activity of the relevant standardisation committees

The activity of the three interested TCs has been monitored, and the progress of the standardisation works included in the D5.5 ‘Report on the Standardisation Landscape and Applicable Standards’ as well as the identification of other developments that could be relevant for BIO-SUSHY, have been updated as follows. In addition, the activity of the relevant standardisation committees is continuously monitored.

CEN/TC 134 “Resilient and textile floor covering”

No relevant standards under development were identified by partners in D5.5. Nowadays, in this TC there are currently 16 documents under development (<https://standards.cencenelec.eu/>), some of them could be considered relevant for the consortium.

Table 3 - Update of the CEN/TC 134 standards under development

Reference	Document title	Scope
prEN 15115 (Review of EN 15115:2006)	Textile floor coverings - Determination of sensitivity to spilled water	This document specifies a method to determine the sensitivity of a textile floor covering for appearance change after water has been spilled and dried on the surface. This change can be: a) a colour change; b) a change in structure; c) migration and concentration of chemicals coming from the product. NOTE A concentration of chemicals on a part of the surface can cause accelerated uneven soiling of textile floor coverings.

CEN/TC 194 “Utensils in contact with food”

Regarding CEN/TC 194, the status of the relevant standards under development identified in D5.5 is summarised in the following table. In addition, in this TC there are currently 16 documents under development (<https://standards.cencenelec.eu/>), some of them could be considered relevant for the consortium.

Table 4 - Update of the CEN/TC 194 standards under development

Reference	Document title	Scope
prEN 1186-1 rev (Review of EN 1186-1:2002)	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics - Part 1: Guide to the selection of conditions and test methods for overall migration	This part of this European Prestandard provides a guide to the selection of the appropriate conditions and methods of test for the determination of overall migration into food simulants from plastics which are intended to come into contact with foodstuffs.
prEN 13130-1 rev (Review of EN 13130-1:2004)	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 1: Guide to test methods for the specific migration of substances from plastics to foods and food simulants and the determination of substances in plastics and the selection of conditions of exposure to food simulants evaluation and specification of Key Performance Indicators for PBF-LB/M processes	This part of this European Standard provides a guide to the selection of the appropriate conditions of contact of food simulants with the test article before the determination of specific migration of those substances subject to a migration limit

CEN/TC 392 “Cosmetics”

No relevant standards under development were identified by partners in D5.5. Nowadays, in this TC there are currently 2 documents under development (<https://standards.cencenelec.eu/>) but they are not related with the scope of BIO-SUSHY.

CEN/TC 411 “Biobased Products”

Apart from the standards developed by the previous three main interested technical committees, the evaluation of the biobased content in BIO-SUSHY is crucial. It has been pointed out the difficulty related to the use of the appropriate standard to evaluate the biobased content in BIO-SUSHY coatings. In this regard, it is important to consider the set of standards developed by CEN/TC 411.

The European Commission focusses on biobased products, describing methods for biobased content determination, requirements for sustainability assessment and how to communicate about them in the value chain. By using these standards, producers can present and promote their biobased products in the same understandable way.

Together with the standards identified in the D5.5 there are other standards that could be considered. There are standards for measuring and reporting on biobased content, sustainability aspects and terminology. These standards are summarized in the following table (Table 5).

Table 5 – Relevant Standards from CEN/TC 411

Reference	Document title
<i>Bio base content determination</i>	
EN 16785-1:2015	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 1: Determination of the bio-based content using the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis
EN 16785-2:2018	Bio-based product - Bio-based content - Part 2: Determination of the bio-based content using the material balance method
EN 16640:2017/AC:2017	Bio-based products - Determination of the bio-based carbon content of products using the radiocarbon method
CEN/TR 16721:2014	Bio-based products - Overview of methods to determine the bio based content
EN 17351:2020	Bio-based products - Determination of the oxygen content using an elemental analyser
<i>Sustainability</i>	
EN 16760:2015	Bio-based products - Life Cycle Assessment
EN 16751:2016	Bio-based products - Sustainability criteria
CEN/TR 16957:2016	Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase
CEN/TR 17341:2019	Bio-based products - Examples of reporting on sustainability criteria
<i>Terminology</i>	
EN 16575:2014	Bio-based products – Vocabulary
EN 16848:2016	Bio-based products - Template for B2B reporting and communication of characteristics - Data sheet'
EN 16935:2017	Bio-based products - Business-to-Consumer communication and claims
EN 16766:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based solvents - Requirements test methods

2. Further contact with the standardisation committees

Between M24 and M32, an updated summary of the project will be provided to the three interested TCs. In addition, the need to participate in any of their plenary meetings will be discussed to explain the technical aspects of the project in more detail and to strategize a potential contribution to standardisation. The contribution of the technical partners will be needed for this purpose. Furthermore, as mentioned before, further interaction with CEN/TC 139 and CEN/TC 248 will be promoted based on the new outcome of this use case in the project.

3. Participation of BIO-SUSHY partners in standardisation technical committees

To date, none of the BIO-SUSHY partners have participated in plenary meetings of the main interested technical committees. In addition, a questionnaire (**Annex A**) was shared with all BIO-SUSHY partners to gather information about their relationship with standardisation and to know if any of them is participating in standardization technical committees related to the project.

The feedback obtained revealed that:

- For most of the partners, BIO-SUSHY is the first European project in which they are participating with a specific task focused on standardisation activities.
- Regarding the participation of partners in technical committees, subcommittees or working groups related with the scope of BIO-SUSHY, there are three partners that have been involved in technical committees. These committees are the CEN/TC 352 "Nanotechnologies", the Textile-Clothing Standardization Bureau (BNITH) manager by IFTH by delegation from AFNOR and the VDI – The Association of German Engineers. In addition, there is one partner (Materia Nova) that is planning to participate in TCs.

4. Establishment of formal liaison of BIO-SUSHY with standardisation committees

This option has not been evaluated to date and it has not been proposed by any of the committees interested in the project up to date.

2.3. Standardisation process

The first steps towards the transfer of project results to standards are scheduled after the current deliverable and during the second half of the project, however, a questionnaire (**Annex A**) was shared with all partners to gather information relevant for the standardisation process.

The objectives of this questionnaire were:

1. Identify the standards that are being used within the project.
2. Test the degree of satisfaction with them.
3. Identify any gap or modification that could be edited on standards to cover further functionalities or to be adapted to specific tasks/research/processes, etc.
4. Identify results or topics that can be candidates to go through a standardisation process.

According to the feedback received, 3 out of 10 partners are using standards within the project. These standards are summarized in the following table (Table 6).

Table 6 – Standards that are being used within the project

Standard reference	Title	Technical committee
ISO16532-2:2007	Paper and board — Determination of grease resistance	ISO/TC 6/SC 2 Test methods and quality specifications for paper and board
EN ISO 14855-2:2018	Determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastic materials under controlled composting conditions — Method by analysis of evolved carbon dioxide Part 2: Gravimetric measurement of carbon dioxide evolved in a laboratory-scale test	CEN/TC 249 Plastics
EN ISO 4920:2013-01	Textile fabrics - Determination of resistance to surface wetting (spray test)	CEN/TC 248 Textiles and textiles products
ISO 14419:2010-05	Textiles - Oil repellency - Hydrocarbon resistance test	ISO/TC 38/SC 2 Textiles

ISO 5077:2022	Textiles — Determination of dimensional change in washing and drying	ISO/TC 38/SC 2 Textiles
ISO 4920:2012	Textile fabrics — Determination of resistance to surface wetting (spray test)	ISO/TC 38/SC 2 Textiles
ISO 9865:1991	Textiles — Determination of water repellency of fabrics by the Bundesmann rain-shower test	ISO/TC 38/SC 2 Textiles
ISO 12945-1:2020	Textiles — Determination of fabric propensity to surface pilling, fuzzing or matting	ISO/TC 38/SC 24 Conditioning atmospheres and physical tests for textile fabrics
ISO 12947-2:2016	Textiles — Determination of the abrasion resistance of fabrics by the Martindale method	ISO/TC 38/SC 24 Conditioning atmospheres and physical tests for textile fabrics
ISO 1513:2010	Paints and varnishes — Examination and preparation of test samples	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 1514:2016	Paints and varnishes — Standard panels for testing	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 1518-1:2023	Paints and varnishes — Determination of scratch resistance — Part 1: Constant-loading method	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 2409:2020	Paints and varnishes — Cross-cut test	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 2812-1:2017	Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to liquids — Part 1: Immersion in liquids other than water	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 2812-2:2018	Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to liquids — Part 2: Water immersion method	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 2884-1:1999	Paints and varnishes — Determination of viscosity using rotary viscometers — Part 1: Cone-and-plate viscometer operated at a high rate of shear	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes

<p>ISO 3251:2019</p>	<p>Paints, varnishes and plastics — Determination of non-volatile-matter content</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 4628-1:2016</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 1: General introduction and designation system</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 4628-2:2016</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 2: Assessment of degree of blistering</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 4628-4:2016</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of degradation of coatings — Designation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 4: Assessment of degree of cracking</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 4628-5:2022</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Evaluation of quantity and size of defects, and of intensity of uniform changes in appearance — Part 5: Assessment of degree of flaking</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 6270-2:2017</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Determination of resistance to humidity — Part 2: Condensation (in-cabinet exposure with heated water reservoir)</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>
<p>ISO 11998:2006</p>	<p>Paints and varnishes — Determination of wet-scrub resistance and cleanability of coatings</p>	<p>ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes</p>

ISO 15184:2020	Paints and varnishes — Determination of film hardness by pencil test	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 8130-1:2019	Coating powders — Part 1: Determination of particle size distribution by sieving	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 8130-15:2023	Coating powders — Part 15: Rheology	ISO/TC 35 Paints and Varnishes
ISO 9001:2015	Quality management systems — Requirements	ISO/TC 176/SC 2 Quality Systems
ISO14001:2015	Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use	ISO/TC 207/SC 1 Environmental management systems
ISO14040:2006	Life cycle assessment - Principles and framework	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment
ISO14044:2006	Life cycle assessment - Requirements and guidelines	ISO/TC 207/SC 5 Life cycle assessment

Regarding the degree to which the standards meet the needs of the partners in the project, all of them agree that the standards are completely useful for their purpose and no gaps were identified. There is a specific mention to the standard ISO 14419:2010 for textile characterization (water and oil repellency) which defines a protocol that cannot be easily followed as it requires specific equipment. In this sense, the same conditions of the standard are being replicated.

In relation to the identification of results that could serve as the foundation for the development of new standards, no clear ideas have been stated to date. In the questionnaire, there were a few ideas related to this topic:

- The first one concerns the characterization of oleophobicity, as there are no existing standards (except for textiles) and everyone uses their own method.
- The second one involves the development of standards for sliding angle measurements.
- The last one pertains to the development of standards for automatic computational workflows.

In addition, the consortium points out that the development of standards within the projects will benefit the consistency, characterization, and comparison of the products that already exist on the market with those provided by the BIO-SUSHY project.

In this regard, considering the project’s timeline, new results and ideas contributing to standardisation will emerge in the coming months during the second half of the project. Additionally, after updating the relevant TCs, their interest in the project will be taken into account.

Depending on the feedback that the project will receive from relevant TCs, the outcome of the project, and the relevant topics that partners will identify, the ‘standardisation workshop’ or CWA may be the

most suitable path in the standardisation process. The decisions made, the actions taken, and the results achieved will be properly documented in D5.8 (final version; M48).

3. Update of the implementation

An update of the summary of the tentative dates and the responsible for the actions is included in the next table:

Table 7 – Summary of the actions in the strategy towards a contribution to standardisation

Action	Responsible	Month
First contacts with the standardisation committees in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M10 - M15
Updates on the standardisation landscape	UNE	Continuous but formally at M15 M24 M36
Provision of updated report/information to the standardisation committees identified in Table 1	UNE (content provided by the Coordinator)	M24 M30 Whenever it is demanded
Face to face interaction with the relevant standardisation committees	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	When relevant
Dedicated standardisation session	UNE	M24 - M30
Standardisation process	UNE and Coordinator/Partners	M30 - M48

4. Conclusions

The engagement with the standardisation system aims to disseminate the project's objectives and results within the standardisation community and facilitate future contributions to standardisation. This effort is concentrated on the actions outlined in sections 2.1 and 2.2.

Relevant information about BIO-SUSHY was delivered to the selected standardization committees in the fields of bio-based coatings, water and oil repellency, safe and sustainable by design manufacturing approaches and targeting the textile, food packaging, and cosmetic markets. The aim of this first communication was to introduce the project, show the link with the relevant standardisation committees and pulse their interest and their view about a later contribution to standardisation from the project.

As a result of this communication, positive feedback was received from CEN/TC 134, CEN/TC 194 and CEN/TC 392. Everyone expressed an interest in staying updated on the project's progress and having the results and findings shared with them. To keep them engaged in the project, they will be updated on the project's progress and their feedback will be discussed within the project.

Next phase in Standardisation activities in BIO-SUSHY will be aimed to make an effective contribution to standardisation as described in 2.3. In this regard, the feedback received from all partners indicated that, on one hand, all the standards being used in the project meet their requirements and no gaps have been identified. On the other hand, although some topics have been stated, no results have been identified that could serve as the seed for the development of new standards up to now. With the aim of assisting partners, an internal workshop will be held to identify which results could serve as the foundation for contributing to standardisation and to outline the process for the development of hypothetical CEN and CENELEC Workshop Agreements (CWAs) in the project.

The actions and results of the standardisation process will be collected in D5.8 (third and ultimate version) at M48.

ANNEX A: Questionnaire

This document presents the information related to the questionnaire about standardisation carried out among BIO-SUSHY partners during May and June 2024. It contains the questions and the answers of each participant. in order to study future standardisation possibilities according to the objectives of the Task 5.4 of the project.

The questionnaire covers the following aspects:

- Participation in European standardisation technical committees related to BIO-SUSHY project
- Standards being used for the development of BIO-SUSHY tasks
- Degree of satisfaction with used standards and aspects to be improved
- Aspects not covered by standards that could/should be standardized
- BIO-SUSHY results that could be subject of standardization
- European legislation affecting partners' tasks

After the filling period, the questionnaire was answered by the 10 partners, providing valuable information that is analysed in this D5.7.

QUESTIONS about previous participation in standardisation activities

In this section, we ask partners about their previous participation in standardisation activities (If any).

QUESTION 1

Besides BIO-SUSHY, have you or your organisation ever participated in Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe projects with UNE (The Spanish Association for Standardisation) or others national standardisation bodies (i.e, DIN, IPQ, AFNOR, etc.)?

QUESTION 2

If your answer to the previous question was YES, please indicate the name of the project or some of them:

QUESTION 3

Is your organisation participating in any European, international or national standardisation technical committee (TC), working group or similar group related to the BIO-SUSHY project?

QUESTION 4

Based in your previous answer, please specify the technical committee, working group or similar your organisation is participating or is willing to participate:

QUESTION 5

Please specify the reasons why you are participating in a technical committee or group (several answers are possible)

QUESTION 6

Would you be interested in participating in technical meetings with technical committees that are interested in the project? (In these types of meetings, technical partners will need to explain the project's results to the experts involved in committees that are developing standards related to BIO-SUSHY)

ANSWERS about previous participation in standardisation activities

PARTNER	ANSWERS					
	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6
SiKEMIA	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	NO	-	-	YES
Wood K-Plus	NO, but we are planning to participate in new projects	-	YES, by attending meetings and by correspondence	Powder coating of MDF and wood-based materials (https://www.vdi.de/richtlinien/details/vdi-2015-blatt-1-pulverbeschichtung-von-mdf-und-anderen-holzwerkstoffen)	To establish better levels of quality, performance, interoperability, etc...	N/A

AXIA Innovation	YES, my organisation has participated	-	NO	-	-	N/A
ZSI	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	NO	-	-	YES
ProtoQSAR	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	NO	-	-	YES
AcumenIST	YES, I have participated	NanoReg; plus: direct work with standardisation bodies	YES, by attending meetings and by correspondence	CEN/TC 352 - several TC or groups	Others	YES
RESCOLL	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	NO	-	-	N/A
MATERIA NOVA	NO, but we are	-	NO	Not identified	To establish better levels of	YES

	planning to participate in new projects				quality, performance, interoperability, etc..., To make contacts with other stakeholders	
IFTH	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	YES, by attending meetings and by correspondence	In France, the standardisation of the Textile and Clothing sectors is the responsibility of the Textile-Clothing Standardisation Bureau (BNITH) manager by IFTH by délégation from AFNOR	To influence in the content of standards according my products/service, To establish better levels of quality, performance, interoperability, etc...	N/A
CNR	NO, this is the first project in which we are working with standardisation	-	NO	-	-	N/A

ANALYSIS about previous participation in standardisation activities

The first question reveals that for 6 out of 11 of the partners, BIO-SUSHY is the first European project in which they are participating with a specific task focused on standardisation activities. However, the organizations of two of the partners (AcumenIST and AXIA) have already been involved in standardisation activities within other projects, as for example NanoReg, a project focused on the development and design of a common European approach to the regulatory testing of nanomaterials. In addition, there is one partner (Materia Nova) that is planning to participate in additional projects with the aim of contributing to standardisation.

Figure 1. Summary of the answers for Question 1.

Regarding the participation of partners in technical committees, subcommittees or working groups related with the scope of BIO-SUSHY, there are three partners (Wood K Plus, AcumenIST and IFTH) that have been involved in technical committees. In addition, there is one partner (Materia Nova) that is planning to participate in TCs.

Figure 2. Summary of the answers for Question 3.

Partners consider that the participation in technical committees offers numerous advantages as for example:

- The influence in the content of standards according product specifications
- The establishment of better levels of quality, performance, interoperability, etc.
- The possibility to make contacts with other stakeholders.

Figure 3. Summary of the answers for Question 5.

Finally, most of the partners are inclined to participate in technical meetings with TCs.

Figure 4. Summary of the answers for Question 6.

QUESTIONS about the use of standards

In this section, we ask you to specify the most relevant European or international standards identified in Deliverable D5.5 or others you are working with for your tasks in BIO-SUSHY, their degree of fulfilment regarding your needs with a detailed answer.

QUESTION 7

Within the framework of the BIO-SUSHY project and (directly or indirectly) related to your tasks in the project, is your organisation using European (EN) or international standards (ISO) or other standards among those identified in Deliverable D5.5?

QUESTION 8

Please indicate the Name/Number/Reference of the standard/s

QUESTION 9

Please specify the degree of fulfilment with your needs of the standards you are using

QUESTION 10

Please detail your previous answer (one answer by each standard used)

ANSWERS about the use of standards

PARTNER	ANSWERS			
	#7	#8	#9	#10
SiKEMIA	NO	-	-	-
Wood K-Plus	YES	ISO 16532-2 ; EN14855	The standard is totally useful for our purposes	-
AXIA Innovation	NO	-	-	-
ZSI	NO	-	-	-
ProtoQSAR	NO	-	-	-
AcumenIST	NO	-	-	-
RESCOLL	YES	NF EN ISO 49202013-01 and NF EN ISO 144192010-05	The standard is totally useful for our purposes	<i>See below</i>
MATERIA NOVA	YES	R&D organization: ISO9001:2015; ISO14001:2015; LCA: ISO14040:2006 et ISO14044:2006; ISO/TC35 ISO (see table 4 in D5.5)	The standard is totally useful for our purposes	-
IFTH	YES		-	-
CNR	NO	-	-	-

ANALYSIS about the use of standards

It has to be considered that 36% of the partners are using standards within BIO-SUSHY.

Figure 5. Summary of the answers for Question 7.

In addition, it is considered unanimously that these standards are useful for their purposes and no edition is needed. In particular, it is mentioned that for performing textile characterizations (water and oil repellency), the protocol described in EN ISO 14419:2010 is used. However, since the same equipment is not available, they attempt to replicate it.

Figure 6. Summary of the answers for Question 9.

QUESTIONS about the reason to use standards

QUESTION 11

Please specify the reasons why you are using standards related to your tasks (several answers are possible)

ANSWERS about the reason to use standards

Figure 7. Summary of the answers for Question 11.

ANALYSIS about the reason to use standards

For BIO-SUSHY partners one of the main reasons for using standards is to meet legislation or regulation requirements. The second reason is to achieve better levels of quality, performance and interoperability. Only two partners consider that the use of standards allows to ensure safety of workers and other people.

QUESTIONS about new standards or gaps in standardisation

QUESTION 12

Based on the progress of the project up to date, do you think some aspect (technical, performance, efficiency, reliability, interoperability or quality requirements) of your task not included in a standard should be standardised to facilitate design, manufacturing, trade, safety, relation among stakeholders, etc.?

QUESTION 13

If your answer has been YES, please detail for which task, specific aspects and possible interested sectors

QUESTION 14

If you are using any standard, have you identified any gap or modification that could be edited to cover further functionalities or to be adapted to your tasks/research/processes, etc.?

ANSWERS about new standards or gaps in standardisation

PARTNER	ANSWERS		
	#12	#13	#14
SiKEMIA	YES	T2.4 Pilot Application	
Wood K-Plus	N/A	-	Not so far yet
AXIA Innovation	N/A	-	
ZSI	YES	<p>I am active in the domain of social acceptance. Even though this is not very much related to standards at first sight, there are already other domains of standardisation where issues like public trust and other societal issues become part of standardisation (for instance in AI standardisation). Especially for example with regards to risk governance and general sustainability, I think there would be space for standardisation efforts. Currently it is still a bit early to specify this further.</p>	Not yet, too early at the moment.
ProtoQSAR	NO	-	
AcumenIST	N/A	-	
RESCOLL	YES	-	
MATERIA NOVA	NO	<p>Oleophobicity characterization: no standard existing (except textile maybe); everybody uses its own</p>	

		method; Sliding angle measurement	
IFTH	YES	-	Not yet at this stage of the project
CNR	N/A	Automatic computational workflow - sector Computational Modelling	Not yet

Figure 8. Summary of the answers for Question 12.

ANALYSIS new standards or gaps in standardisation

Up to date, there are only three ideas for the development of new standards. The first one has to do with the oleophobicity characterization as there are no standards existing and everybody uses its own method. The second one has to do with the development of standards for sliding angle measurements. The last one is related to the development of standards for automatic computational workflow. Additionally, the standards being used in the project are considered to satisfy all the necessary requirements, with no perceived gaps that could be modified or edited.

QUESTIONS about standards to market the results

QUESTION 15

Could a standard be beneficial for marketing the results of BIO-SUSHY in the future?

QUESTION 16

If your answer has been YES, please specify for which component/deliverable and possible interested sectors

ANSWERS about standards to market the results

PARTNER	ANSWERS	
	#15	#16
SIKEMIA	YES	For consistency, measurement, and comparison of textile and packaging products already on the market to those provide by the Bio-SUSHY project.
Wood K-Plus	YES	Coating of paper for packaging applications
AXIA Innovation	YES	Coating formulations
ZSI	N/A	
ProtoQSAR	N/A	
AcumenIST	YES	
RESCOLL	YES	
MATERIA NOVA	N/A	
IFTH	YES	For wettability/sliding properties evaluation
CNR	YES	For textile performances (Technical apparel)

ANALYSIS about standards to market the results

Figure 9. Summary of the answers for Question 15.

Most of the partners consider that the development of new standards could be beneficial for marketing project results. In particular, it is mentioned that standards for the measurement and

comparison of textile and packaging products already on the market to those provided by the Bio-SUSHY project will be beneficial.

QUESTIONS about IPR & patent policies in CEN and ISO

QUESTION 17

An increasing number of standards based on patented technology are being successfully and widely developed. Nevertheless, to avoid patent rights problems that may arise when developing standards, CEN-CENELEC has developed a document to provide practical guidance on this subject. Do you know the IPR & Patents policies applied by CEN and ISO? (Link to CEN CENELEC IPR website, Link to ISO IPR website)

ANSWERS about IPR & patent polices in CEN and ISO

Figure 10. Summary of the answers for Question 17.

ANALYSIS about IPR & patent polices in CEN and ISO

There is only one partner aware of the IPR and patent policy in CEN and ISO. These policies will be explained during the next meeting and they will be considered in the standardisation activities within the project.

QUESTIONS about applicable legislation

QUESTION 18

Is your BIO-SUSHY task/activity affected by any European legislation (Directives, regulations...)?

QUESTION 19

If your answer to the previous question was YES, please specify the task/activity and relevant legislation concerned

ANSWERS about applicable legislation

Figure 11. Summary of the answers for Question 18

ANALYSIS about applicable legislation

The legislation considered by project partners pertains to the prohibition of PFAS (**Regulation (EC) N° 1907/2006** - Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)) and the single use plastic directive (**Directive (EU) 2019/904**).

